

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL INSTRUMENTS IN THE WORK OF HEALTHCARE ORGANIZATIONS

Beissegul A.

PhD, MBA, doctoral Student of Business Administration

Abstract

There are cultural and regulatory barriers to the adoption of digital health technologies around the world, with the extent of these varying from country to country. However, increasing capabilities and falling costs of upgrading mean that financial barriers are becoming less relevant. The focus is on how developments in digital technologies and associated devices can deliver services and enable patients, carers and healthcare professionals to connect to information, data and improve the quality and outcomes of health and social care. In this article we provide an overview of the introduction of digital instruments in the work of healthcare organizations.

Keywords: digital technologies, digitalization, digitalization of healthcare, healthcare management, innovations in healthcare.

A growing body of research shows that digital technologies, including mobile technologies, have the potential to reduce health care costs, expand access, and improve outcomes. The power and reach of technology can improve access, overcome geographic distance and lack of facilities, while providing a more universal and personalized approach to health care.

New technologies in healthcare are used to improve the quality of medical care, the efficiency of processes, and the availability of medical services. Let us note several ways in which new technologies are used.

Diagnosis and treatment. New technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and data analytics are used to analyze medical data and images, helping doctors diagnose diseases, determine the best treatment, and monitor outcomes [1].

Telemedicine and remote monitoring. With the help of new technologies, patients can receive medical care remotely via video and monitor their health using wearable devices and mobile apps.

Electronic medical records. New technologies allow for the efficient storage, sharing, and analysis of patient medical data, improving the availability of information to medical staff and improving care coordination.

Robotics and automation. In some cases, new technologies such as robotics and automated systems are used to perform certain medical procedures, surgeries, and other manipulations [2].

Biomedical engineering and medical device development. New technologies enable the development of more efficient and innovative medical devices, hardware, and technologies for diagnosing, treating, and monitoring diseases.

Genomics and personalized medicine. New technologies in genomics and bioinformatics enable the analysis of patients' genetic data and the development of personalized approaches to treatment and care.

Education and learning platforms. New technologies are used to create learning platforms and online courses that help healthcare professionals and students expand their knowledge and skills.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is playing an increasingly important role in the digital healthcare services

ecosystem. Here are some ways in which AI is being integrated into these services:

Diagnosis and prognosis, where AI is used to analyze medical data, including symptoms, images, and test results, to help doctors diagnose diseases and predict treatment outcomes.

Personalized care, where AI can analyze a patient's medical data and offer personalized treatment and care approaches based on individual characteristics, genetic analysis, and medical history.

Telemedicine and Virtual Assistants (Personal Health Assistants) - AI is used to automate telemedicine processes, including chatbots and virtual assistants that can provide patients with information about diseases, prescriptions, etc., as well as to conduct initial consultations [3].

Process automation and data management are greatly simplified when AI helps automate healthcare processes such as medical data management, appointment scheduling, resource optimization, and predicting healthcare needs.

Medical imaging and analysis - AI is used to analyze medical images such as X-rays, computed tomography (CT) scans, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans to help doctors identify abnormalities and detect early signs of disease.

Big data analytics and epidemic prediction - The use of AI helps healthcare organizations respond to changing circumstances and take steps to prevent the spread of diseases.

The digital transformation is based on 5P technology. The application of 5P technology in medicine is very useful and promising. This concept describes five main aspects that should be taken into account when developing and implementing technologies:

1) **Prediction -** involves using data and analytics to predict the likelihood of patients developing diseases or predicting treatment outcomes. For example, machine learning algorithms can analyze a patient's medical data and predict the likelihood of complications or the need for additional medical procedures.

2) **Prevention -** involves organizing general medical examinations of the population, as well as using technologies to prevent the development of diseases

and reduce the risk of their occurrence. For example, mobile applications can help patients lead a healthy lifestyle by providing recommendations on nutrition, physical activity, and stress management.

3) Personalization - means adapting health care to the individual needs and characteristics of the patient. Technologies can be used to develop personalized treatment and care plans considering the genetic characteristics, medical history, and preferences of the patient.

4) Participation - involves patients in the process of decision-making and managing their health. Technologies such as mobile gadgets and apps allow patients to track their health indicators, participate in monitoring and feedback, and take an active part in the treatment process.

5) Progress - refers to the use of technology to continually improve medical practice and improve treatment outcomes. This may include the introduction of innovative diagnostic and treatment methods, as well as data analysis and feedback to optimize healthcare processes [4].

The application of 5P technology in medicine has a significant impact on the architecture of the healthcare system, its improvement and can be manifested in the following aspects.

To successfully predict, prevent and personalize healthcare, it is necessary to have access to a variety of patient data sources, including medical history, laboratory results, genetic information and data on behavioral health factors. This requires the development of data collection and integration systems and analytical platforms capable of processing and analyzing huge amounts of information.

To ensure patient participation in the treatment process and health management, it is necessary to create digital platforms and applications that will provide access to medical information, self-monitoring tools and the ability to communicate with medical personnel. This will also automate the processes of making an appointment, receiving prescriptions and ordering medical services.

Progressive diagnostic and treatment methods, such as genetic testing, telemedicine consultations, the use of artificial intelligence to analyze medical data and make decisions require the development and implementation of specialized medical applications and platforms. This may include the development of machine learning algorithms and research into new methods of processing and analyzing medical data. With the increasing number of digital systems and technologies in healthcare, it is important to ensure their compatibility and standardization to ensure effective interaction between different systems and the exchange of data between them. This requires the development of common standards and protocols for data exchange in healthcare. With the development of new technologies and methods of service, it is necessary to provide training to medical personnel and patients on the use of new tools and platforms, which includes conducting training programs, webinars and developing educational materials [5].

Effective functioning of the new architecture requires improvement of business processes of service provision, data processing, implementation of innovative technologies and ensuring compatibility and standardization of various system components. The implementation of 5P technology in medicine affects the requirements for medical personnel and their competencies. Let us note several key changes and requirements.

Medical personnel must have skills in working with digital technologies and an understanding of the principles of operation of medical information systems. This includes the ability to use electronic medical records, mobile health applications, telemedicine platforms and other digital tools.

In light of the use of data analytics to predict and prevent diseases, medical personnel must have the skills to analyze large amounts of information and interpret the results of analytical algorithms.

With the development of telemedicine and increased interaction with patients through digital platforms, medical personnel must be able to effectively communicate with patients remotely, via video, chat and other means of communication.

Medical personnel must regularly undergo training and refresher courses on the use of new technologies and service methods. Educational programs should include training in digital skills in marketing, management, data analytics, telemedicine and other modern aspects of medical practice [6].

With the increasing amount of digital patient data, healthcare personnel must strictly adhere to data security and privacy regulations to prevent data leaks and unauthorized access to medical information.

Overall, healthcare personnel must be prepared to work in a digital environment, have a wide range of skills and competencies, and be prepared to adapt to the ever-changing medical practice and technological innovations.

The use of 5P technology in medicine allows to increase the efficiency and quality of medical care, make it more personalized and accessible to patients, and stimulates continuous development and improvement.

New technologies and artificial intelligence play a key role in modern medicine, providing tools and solutions to increase the efficiency of healthcare, improve the quality of medical care and expand the availability of medical services.

Devices, gadgets and applications help people better understand their health, improve their lifestyle, effectively manage diseases and receive medical care and advice at a time and place convenient for them.

This transformation is leading to changes in the structure and competencies of medical personnel, requiring them to have greater digital literacy, analytical skills, and the ability to work with patients remotely. Data security and privacy standards are becoming increasingly important in the context of the expanding digitalization of the medical field.

References

1. Kahneman, D. (2014) Contours of bounded rationality: the possibility of intuitive judgments and choice. *Institute of Privatization and Management*, 3 (12), 540—592
2. ÖZTÜRK, M., & BATUM, T. P. (2019). How housing brands use social media in their marketing communications?: A content analysis. *Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 17(33), 111–135. <https://doi.org/10.35408/comuybd.449009>
3. Tikhomirova, V. I., & Gibalov, V. G. (2015). Online marketing in the fitness industry. *Fundamental and Applied Researches: Challenges and Results*, 20, 177–184.
4. Pinto, M. B., & Yagnik, A. (2016). Fit for life: A content analysis of fitness tracker brands use of Facebook in social media marketing. *Journal of Brand Management*, 24(1), 49–67. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41262-016-0014-4>
5. Bolia, B., Sumi, J., & Manoj, Jha. K. (2016). Cognitive dissonance: A review of causes and marketing implications. *Researchers World: Journal of Arts, Science and Commerce*, 7(2), 63–76. <https://doi.org/10.18843/rwjasc/v7i2/06>
6. West, D., Ford, J., Ibrahim, E., & Montecchi, M. (2022). Service marketing strategies. *Strategic Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hebz/9780198856764.003.0011>